

The Inner Search

Aman Chawla

June 8, 2025

Abstract

In this note the author relates the inner illumination to the physical cosmos and thereby motivates the inner search.

Does the light of the Divine illuminate the cosmos? If so, will it always illuminate it, or will there be a time when the cosmos will be devoid of Divine light? This is related to the relation between illumination and existence. Is light the essence of existence? If so packets of light energy have supramental light [1] as their essence. In other words, the nonlocal infinite is the substratum of the local finite. How does one delve into the substratum? One way is to probe one's own inner body and another way is to calm the mind, making it easier to go within. For within is the substratum, the nonlocal infinite, colorless, attribute-less.

References

- [1] Sri Aurobindo. *The life divine*. Lotus Press, 1990.